

Improving Language Surrounding Sex and Gender, and Making Unit Materials More Accessible

A guide prepared by Diva Chaudhary under the supervision of Dr Hendrika Duivenvoorden

The following contains some tips for educators to aid them in improving their course materials in the areas of sex, gender, and accessibility. Doing so will ensure all students feel included and prioritised in their learning.

Sex and Gender

- If educators feel comfortable doing so, it is helpful for students if educators include their pronouns in introductory material, such as next to their contact information or when introducing themselves for the first time in person
 - This prevents inaccurate assumptions and normalises providing pronouns in everyday life
- Don't assume an individual's gender or pronouns, default to 'they' or use their preferred name in person, as well as in online communication
- If your teaching in any way connects to sex and/or gender - acknowledge there is a difference between sex and gender, and give examples as to how that will be implemented in your specific teaching context. When discussing sex, highlight there is much greater diversity than the female/male binary.
- Questions should be phrased so that students don't have to assume a gender based solely on a given name. Where appropriate, include diverse examples of gender/relationships in scenarios, questions and assessments
- It is more inclusive to default to using "they / them" pronouns when describing scenarios or examples where gender is irrelevant. Or you may be more comfortable using non-gendered terms such as "this/that individual", "this/that person",

Some of these recommendations are based on research led by Hendrika, please reach out to Hendrika.Duivenvoorden@monash.edu if you would like to discuss this further

In the area of human biology specifically:

- It is more accurate and inclusive to separate gender from human anatomy. Of particular note is to avoid woman/women and man/men when discussing anatomy or genetics. However, seemingly 'biological' terms are based on a binary that may not match with someone's gender identity.
 - Commonly used words and some suggested replacements for different contexts are:
 - Female → XX individual, egg-producing individual, person with a uterus
 - Male → XY individual, sperm-producing individual, person with testes
 - Mother → egg parent
 - Father → sperm parent

- When using pedigree charts as examples, lecturers are encouraged to increase representation by including gender diverse and binary transgender individuals

For example:

Gender	Sex		
	Male	Female	Unassigned at Birth
Man/Boy	 UAAB 28y		
Woman/Girl	 UAAB 28y		
Non-binary/Gender Diverse	 UAAB 28y		

AMAB: Assigned Male at birth. AFAB: Assigned Female at birth. UAAB: unassigned at birth.

Reference: Hales, K. G. (2020). Signaling inclusivity in undergraduate biology courses through deliberate framing of genetics topics relevant to gender identity, disability, and race. *CBE—Life Sciences Education*, 19(2), es2.

- [A useful glossary on terms surrounding sex and gender](#)

Accessibility for People with Disabilities

Tips to aid people who use screen readers

- Organise the content linearly - i.e. from up to down, and left to right (unfavourable page layout is the most likely reason a screen reader will crash)
- Additional captioning or alternative text can be included for images
 - These captions should describe the image succinctly, and explain its key purpose
 - To do this in Microsoft Powerpoint: Right click the image, select 'View alt text...' and write the description
 - To do this in Google Slides: Right click the image and select 'Alt text'
- Proofread resources to prevent typos
- Don't use different coloured text to highlight key terms, not all screen readers can detect the colour difference. Bold text, italics and underlined text can be read by most screen readers.
- Include titles for slides that contain a new subject matter - especially if the slide only consists of an image
- Include the key message of the slide at the top, such as through a subtitle, so that listeners are aware of the main subject immediately
- Avoid using shorthand names without prior definition. Hyphens are a particular problem. Screen readers can't distinguish whether the hyphen refers to a minus, en

dash or an em dash. For example “CD8- cell” would be read by a screen reader as “CD eight [em dash] cell” instead of “CD8 minus cell”

- Reach out to DSS to convert important images to tactile images (we have a tactile printer on site in engineering). Cost is much lower than you might expect.
- Avoid sharing resources as PDFs, as they are often difficult to use with screen readers
 - Sharing the content in its original form like a powerpoint or word document is preferred
 - If the file must be shared as a PDF, these are some tips to make it more accessible:
 - First, ensure that the source file is accessible - if a Microsoft app is being used, an easy way to do this is by going to Review → Check Accessibility and following the instructions.
 - Save the document as an accessible PDF - this varies depending on the device, but the different methods of doing so can be found [here](#)
 - More information:
<https://www.sussex.ac.uk/brand/staff/web/accessibility/accessible-word-documents>
 - <https://youtu.be/hKN3dw-ZXvU?feature=shared>

Tips for more accessible graphs

- For line graphs, varying the line thickness, design, shape, as well as colour can make differentiating groups easier
- Instead of using a legend, labelling each line may be more clear

Good example:

[Reference](#)

Presentation tips to aid those who are colourblind

- Some common problematic colour combinations to avoid include:
 - Red and green
 - Green and brown
 - Green and blue
 - Blue and grey
 - Blue and purple
 - Green and grey
 - Green and black
 - Light green and yellow
 - [Reference](#)
- [This website](#) has a tool that allows you to check whether your colour palette is colour blind friendly - there are also some sample palettes at the bottom

- Avoid using coloured text on coloured backgrounds - a dark font on a light background is best
- Bold key words instead of just changing their colour

Other

- “Mental retardation” is considered an outdated and harmful term that still may be included in some older resources - educators are encouraged to change their resources to include more current terminology such as “intellectual disability”